

ISSN 0970-1745

SLRF Impact Factor 2.364

Shodh

**An International Refereed & Peer-Reviewed Research
Journal Related to Higher Education for all Subjects**

प्रधान संपादक

डॉ० सुरेन्द्र षाण्डेय

Year-35 Vol-97 Feb,2018

ISSN 0970-1745

UGC Approved No. 42069 (OLD)

Shodh

(A Refereed Research Journal, Law & Multidisciplinary)

EDITOR IN CHIEF

Dr. Surendra Pandey, Varanasi

EDITOR

Dr. Shailendra Kumar

Prof. Gelina Rousseva

EDITORIAL BOARD

Dr. Mahmoud Sobhi

Al Jouf University, Sakaka (KSA)

Kedar Nath Yadav

Assistant Professor, R.S.K.D. PG College, Jaunpur, U.P. India

Shri Sachin Awasthi

Department of Economics Government College, Aron, Dist-Guna (M.P.)

Dr. Manohar Chitre

Asst. Professor Commerce, Mata Jijabai Girls' P.G. College, Moti Tabela, Indore.

Prof. Rajkumar Singh

F.M.S., Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi (U.P.)

Prof. Rajeswar Pal

Al Jouf University, Sakaka (KSA)

Prof. Sudhaker Singh

Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi (U.P.)

CONTENTS

1.	Bhopal Mass Disaster Litigation: Legal Issues and Outcome *Dr. Dinesh Kumar Gupta	1–8
2.	Right to Health: A distant Dream in West Bengal, a critical analysis *Bhabani Prasad Mishra	9–13
3.	Violence against Women in India: An Overview *Dr. Mallikarjun Yakapur	14–16
4.	Protection of Investors' Interest: An Analytical Study *Pratima Pandey	17–19
5.	Use of ICT for Developing Conceptual Understanding in Chemistry *Prashant Thote	20–25
6.	This paper investigated the stressors *Vipin	26–33
7.	भारतीय राजनीति : सामाजिक संरचना *डॉ० गीता श्रीवास्तव	34–37
8.	Covid – 19 and Policy of Indian Government *Dr. Bhavna Nayak	38–39
9.	बीमा कम्पनियों के नियम व शर्तों में संशोधन की आवश्यकता *डॉ. विश्वास चौहान *दमयंती कटरे	40–42
10.	Good Governance : A Key Tool of Economic Development *Dr. Ajay Kumar Srivasatava	43–46
11.	Economic Disparities among Social Groups: A Case Study of Jaunpur District, Uttar Pradesh *Garima Maurya	47–53
12.	धर्म बनाम मानवता का छद्म रूप *घनश्याम कुमार	54–56
13.	Relevance in the Present Period of the Vedic Period of Eternal Life System: - in Particular Context of Corona Disaster *Prakash Chandra Mishra	57–63
14.	भारत में महिलाओं की वर्तमान स्थिति की, वैदिक तथा मध्यकाल की स्थिति की तुलनात्मक सामाजिक विवेचना *पूजा राय	64–68

Relevance in the Present Period of the Vedic Period of Eternal Life System: - in Particular Context of Corona Disaster

***Prakash Chandra Mishra**

Assistant Professor in Department of Electronics and Instrumentation Engineering, Faculty
of Engineering and Technology, MJP, Rohilkhand University, Bareilly, U.P-243006, INDIA,
Email:prakashchandramishra075@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

There is well-known ancient scripture as शरीरंव्याधिमन्दिरम् when strictly tells us that the chemicals that have been caused by our body structure, on the other hand, they produce disorder defects (cough, bile and vata), there is a possibility of the birth of various diseases, and on the other hand, it also emphasizes the imperative of being sattvik of our ethics, routines, diet, etc., because the diseases are not only physical but also mental. The whole world is suffering from a severe disaster epidemic, even though it is still under the cover of mystery, whether this virus is laboratory-borne or natural, but there is no difference in its fear, it is still continuing its 'slaughter campaign' all over the world. If you analyze this disease in the context of India, you find 'Rescue is the security' which is being adopted by the entire world. It has been a lifestyle prevalent in this country since time immemorial. The research paper presented is an attempt to analyze the process of impact and healing due to the coronavirus in terms of India's primitive, Vedic period eternal tradition, civilization, and culture. This research paper also explores certain formulas of the Veda-described tradition of living with the purity of our ethics and diet, etc., coexistence with nature.

OBJECTIVES

The research paper presented covers the following objectives.

- 1) In addition to scientific therapeutic treatments of the Corona disaster

Explore other treatment and preventive methods:

- 2) Analysis of experiments and the importance of India's ancient culture and tradition at present

RESEARCH TECHNIQUE

The research paper submitted is based on secondary data. After thorough study and analysis of Veda texts, Upanishad, and other mythological texts, conclusions have been obtained and generalization of these conclusions has been attempted on the basis of their co-relation to practical conditions.

FIELD OF RESEARCH

The research paper presented is an analytical effort quoting Vedas, Upanishad, policy texts, and our lifestyle relationships in respect of the current global epidemic. It innovatively defines measures to strengthen immunity and immunity, keeping a sensitive attitude towards the disease.

Key Words: Vedic period, Corona, Virus, Santana Dharma, Disaster, Lifestyle, Immunity.

INTRODUCTION

Even before the corona (covid-19) pandemic, there have been many epidemics in the world like plague, typhoid, typhus, influenza, smallpox (variola), Asian flu, Spanish flu, Hong Kong flu, Mars virus, SARS virus, Ebola virus, Nipah Viruses, Zika Virus and Swine Flu. The global epidemic has always warned the human race not to mess with nature.

The global epidemic reminds us of our old culture and civilization. Nature has been worshiped in Indian culture. Nature gives life. Human beings should not play with things provided by nature. The body is made up of five elements – Earth, Water, fire, air and sky. These elements are located in a specific place in the human body. These five elements are made up of the environment. It is related to nature. Nature is related to culture. Therefore, to live life, one has to stop messing with nature. Culture is made of culture and civilization is citizenship. Indian culture is a continuous music. In modern times man misuse his

knowledge. He has lost his civilization and ancient culture. So, Indian culture has earned its name not only in the country but also abroad. An example of culture is also the way of living, eating and drinking, Vedic activity (Ayurveda) Etc. have been adopted by foreign countries too. Culture has a mathematical relationship with philosophy. Philosophy is the basis of life. Culture is helpful in intellectual and mental development. According to KaviRamdhari Singh "Dinkar" Nskriti life is a way of life. India's culture words from Sanskrit. The word culture is mentioned in the Aitareya Brahmin. The Aitareya is the Brahmin text of the Rigveda. The Rigveda is the treasury of all knowledge and rituals. The Rigveda is the source of human energy. The Rigveda is the treasure of Indian culture and civilization. Culture is the foundation of human being. It is the main of India's nationality. That's why India has made its mark among all over the world [1].

At present, the world is troubled by the corona (Covid-19) epidemic. Due to which many countries of the world have to issue the order of lock down. See the effect of this lock down on nature – air purified, water purified, earth Purified, the sky purified and fire purified. The meaning of the saying is that the environment of the whole world was purified. Nature was a slave to pollution. Nature became free from pollution. Freedom in nature and man is enjoying the free nature in the state of this lock down[2]. Before this, the human was trapped in the polluted nature. The polluted nature causes stress and diseases, while the clean nature gives life. Therefore, every country in the world gets a year. Lock down should be kept for a few days. So that we can give polluted nature the appearance of free nature. History has always been warning us to develop as much as we can. There is no exploitation or destruction of nature. Such development which increases the life expectancy (desire to live) of the human being, that is to increase the age of human, is called development. Otherwise any kind of development will fall in the category of destruction [3].

Gautam Buddha said Tighten the string of the veena as much as the sweet sound comes out. Do not tighten the wire of the veena so much that it breaks. That is, tighten the wire of development as much as is necessary, otherwise in the course of development, the wire of development will break.

Due to the corona epidemic, people are not shaking hands, are not embracing, are taking care of cleanliness, and are adopting namaste (pranam). People of every religion have increased their faith in their God. It means to say that people of every religion have started praying to God to get rid of this disease. It seems that this disease has reminded people of Indian culture and civilization. Now people have been cremated. This was the Indian Vedic culture that we had lost from the Western civilization [4].

In the call of the Prime Minister of India, Shri Narendra Modi, on Sunday, April 05, 2020, all the people should serve against the corona by lighting torches, torches, candles by lighting lamps, doors, balconies, windows, ceilings etc. at 9 o'clock in the night. Thanked the people who stayed. So that the war with the disease like corona virus can be won. Former Prime Minister of India Late People hummed Atal Bihari Bajpai's poem "Aadiyajalne".

Stress is a symbol of negativity. Stress is a factor of darkness. Stress is the cause of the downfall of society. Stress can be overcome by positivity. from darkness, lead me to light. Mrityoramrutnam Gamay – (Brihadaranyakopanishad 1.3.28)

I. INDIAN LIFESTYLE AND PROTECTION FROM DISEASES

The consultation and recommendations of doctors, health experts from almost countries of the world have been specified as guidelines by the governments of the countries concerned in the Corona epidemic that has spread to all countries of the world. With a thorough meditation, it is a vision that the virus (corona) epidemic is protected and safety is healing [5].

Fig.1: Structural View of Coronavirus [5]

It does not mean that the role of drugs in the treatment of this disease is insignificant, but it is an undeniable fact that we will be safe only to protect the country and society.

II. REFERENCES TO SPECIFIED PREVENTIVE MEASURES AND INDIAN LIFE SYSTEM

Physical distance, mouth and nose masks or cloth, washing hands with good soap, protecting materials and other substances from viruses, etc., are measures which are directly or indirectly prevalent as well as certain other measures that give more awareness to the above vigilance. The practices can be viewed in the following way:

1) **Curtain-Practice:** Studying the history of ancient and medieval India, there is a sense that the reasons may have been different, but in India's social system, the veil has always been the same. Women (especially married) were completely covered with a veil at home and on the exit, in addition to public treatment; this practice also had a scientific basis.

Fig.2:A Woman covered with a Veil (Traditional Indian Wearing Culture) [6]

At present, scientists are urging them to do so because the dust and dirt that entered the body through the air and through the nose was protected, as well as the success of preventing the infection of the bacteria virus through its breathing when it came into contact with another [6]. At present also, veil practice is a common thing in villages or small towns. Thus, this ancient practice was a powerful and effective way to prevent external side effects.

2) **Style of greeting:** The interest of India's greetings can be mentioned in the major sanskars of ancient culture. It may be noted that by linking the two hands together, greetings are the most prevalent greeting of India, which includes a sense of respect, as well as a foreign system, a hug, and the possibility of infection of virus bacteria, etc., is also ensured. **Namaste' – the age-old, Indian way of greeting with one's both hands joined together – is one of the secrets to India's resistance to the novel coronavirus [6].** A Vedic tradition of the country, **Namaste** is the way guests are greeted and welcomed in Indian households, at hotels, on airplanes and luxury trains. The coronavirus-hit countries are urging people to change their greeting habits that entail physical contact, like shaking hands, kissing on the cheek, hugging,

and giving high-fives. In India, most people are not accustomed to such greetings that maximize the risks of contracting COVID-19.

Fig.3:A Safe,hygienic, globallyaccepted, old, and everlasting Indian Greeting Style [2]

The coronavirus disaster has also compelled many other countries to adopt this system of greetings. It replaces the most important aspects of India's ancient culture in a new form.

3) **Sense of coexistence with nature:-** “एकोअहंद्वितीयोनास्ति” (Ekoahamdvitiyonaasti) -This Sanskrit statement and expression can be a beauty, powerful and all-welfare when it is quoted from the Srimukh (Mouth) of lord Shree Narayan, but when the so-called best work of God begins to be human beings, there is a fear of natural imbalance, forests, organisms and other natural resources seem to be in the way of protecting their existence, at present, this is the condition of the world. By putting a dive in the ocean of India's glorious Veda tradition, we get the knowledge gem of the then human society and nature relationships, which reflects that the then society is as concerned about the existence and development of natural resources as much as its own life and existence [7].

“वृक्षदेवोभव” (Tree is God); The thinking of respect and conservation of the living devas, the mountains, the reservoirs, the rivers as revered and the conservation of these natural resources was a new life and in response, human beings received the prosperity of healthy environmental water, air, food [8].

Fig.4: Tree is a God [8]

The trend of rapid industrialization, urbanization did not only consciousness our city, the village, when it was converted into concrete forests. At present, the root of respiratory diseases, skin diseases, viral diseases must be located somewhere ' migration from rural life '.

4) **The Process of Food-Water Consumptions:** There is a proverb in Hindi “जैसाखाये अन्नवैसाहोयेमन” (As you eat, as your mind) - It is not just a proverb, but a scientific statement that underlines the importance of our vigilance and awareness towards the selection of bhojan (foods)" [5].

In Vedas, the entire grain cycle is classified into three parts, the treatment of grain growing, food baking intake, and variable disorders. The above is vividly described in Vedas. The organic farming that is being talked about to prevent the excessive use of chemicals, pesticides from the excess use of fertility, and other ill-effects have been an integral part of our agricultural system, which was neither detrimental to the land nor the human being [9].

Fig. 5: Indian Ancient Cooking Process using Soil Pots [9]

Indian food is most popular for its diversity. The variety of foods, spices and dishes that are native to India makes Indian food one of the most wholesome foods in the world. But lately, Indian food has begun to be categorized as unhealthy because it is being linked to high sugar and high carb food which can contribute to high cholesterol. Traditional Indian food, however, is not only healthy, but is also incredibly tasty with a lot of health benefits. Indian food supports immunity, inflammation, brain function and several other functions in the human body which help us to fight with Covid 19 [10].

In addition, a detailed description of cooking and path-up fact is available in Vedic texts. At present, in the context of the coronavirus epidemic, the fact has emerged that our food should contain facts that are nutritious as well as help in increasing the immunity of our body. All health experts are constantly saying that avoiding the use of junk-food, canned foods imported from Western countries, which again proves the scientific and usefulness of the Indian dietary system. According to the season, according to the food season (month-month-Hindu practice), the body was healthy, energetic, and free from weather ill effects by behaving according to the Vedas described in the manner described by consuming food items. In addition, the use of utensils in the Indian system, the fuel used for construction, is very common, it is often conceivable that all the resources were biodegradable, such as soil vessel, wood fuel, paddy husk, leaf containers which were non-polluting, and the food manufactured and served with the help of them was healthy. At present, the duration of the coronavirus on the metal surface is 30-45 minutes, making the fear of infection high. In this sense, the usefulness of leaves, soil containers are more in scanting the spread of infection.

Intake of hot food is another way India abstains from falling prey to the novel coronavirus. Hot food is served everywhere from temples to community kitchens, hotels, households and roadside food stalls. No matter how grand the gastronomic arrangement is at a family function or community event, not serving hot food turns off guests. Be it dosa, idli, biryani and filter coffee in South India, or jalebi and **gulabjamun** in North India, or fish curries in West Bengal, or PavBhaji in Mumbai, or **parathas** in Delhi, everything is served and consumed hot.

Fig. 5: Indian Traditional Food [11]

Intake of spicy food is another secret to India's immunity against the novel coronavirus. The use of spices, including chilies, black pepper, cinnamon, cloves, cumin seeds, turmeric, and ginger enriches Indian food with antibacterial properties – which minimizes risks of contracting viruses and reduces vulnerability to bacterial diseases. No matter if western countries have problems with our habit of cooking and consuming spicy food in day-to-day life.

5.Do Yoga Stay Healthy:A Hindi proverb “योगचित्र-वृत्तिनिरोध” says Yoga is the control of the attitudes and can increase the stabilities of mind. Yoga plays a tremendous role to stabilize the versatility of the mind. It shows that the Indian yoga philosophy is not only confined to keeping the body healthy, but it is also a means of empowering the mind and soul.

Fig.6: Maharishi Patanjali Founder of Yoga[12].

The postures mentioned in yoga have certain postures that give strength to the lungs and respiratory tract in increasing the immunity of the body, whose relevance in the protection of the present corona Mahamari (Epidemic) has been substantiated.

6) **cleanliness:**Indians' habit of washing their hands now and then and the use of water from kitchens to toilets play a great role in keeping the country fenced against the COVID-19 virus. Washing of hands before and after a meal is unique to the Indian way of life in the lower to the upper reaches of society. No household work is done without water, be it coking, washing, or mopping. Though India ranks low on the global hygiene index, Indians use water, not toilet paper in the loo.

III. CONCLUSION

Everlasting, eternal, persistent, all-inclusive expressions, etc., are the unique features of the Indian culture society and the family system. Its root causes can be mentioned in the broad life philosophy of co-

existence, nature love, the use of local resources. Indian cultures believe strictly that “VasudhaivaKutumbakam” (The whole world is a family), “Sarve Bhavantu Sukhinah” (May All be Happy), and “Sarve Santu Niraamayaah” (All be Free from Illness). The global from which the local theory is being emphasized in the local world in the Corona period, it has always been an inseparable part of Archaic Indian culture. The global from local global to local theory is being emphasized in the Corona period; Arwachina has always been an indivisible part of Indian culture. Ultimately, it can be said that the principle of ' who will remain the same ' is going to be established as a vision of future life and it will be possible not only by the indiscreet blindness of western countries but by complying with the policy of ' return to origin ' India does not need to take knowledge from Western countries for the protection of its environment, life movement, and established patterns of knowledge. , there is a need to douche the policy of texts, institutions, and from there, we will get the gems of affordable development, disease-free, healthy society, which will achieve our ultimate goal, “ॐसहनाववतुसहः नौभुनक्तु” (Om SahanaavatuSaha: NauBhunaktu)

REFERENCE

- [1] Kuiper, Franciscus Bernardus Jacobus. Aryans in the Rigveda. Vol. 1. Rodopi, 1991. [2] Harari, Yuval Noah. "The world after coronavirus." Financial Times 20 (2020). [3] Srivastava, Anil K., Lakshmanan Sethuraman, and Neeraj Mishra. "All India occupational therapists' association's initiatives during corona virus disease-2019 pandemic." The Indian Journal of Occupational Therapy 52, no. 2 (2020): 35. [4] Jha, Dwijendra Narayan, and D. N. Jha. Ancient India: In Historical Outline. Manohar Publishers & Distributors, 1998. [5] Marwah, Ashok, and Padma Marwah. "Coronavirus (COVID-19): A protocol for prevention, treatment and control." Journal of Applied and Natural Science (2020): 119-123. [6] Pathak, Krishna Prasad, Tara Gaire, and Mu-Hsing Ho. "Why has COVID-19 not hit the countries like Nepal yet?." Reviews on environmental health 1, no. ahead-of-print (2020). [7] Hojnik, Nataša, Uroš Cvelbar, Gabrijela Tavčar-Kalcher, James L. Walsh, and Igor Križaj. "Mycotoxin decontamination of food: cold atmospheric pressure plasma versus "classic" decontamination." Toxins 9, no. 5 (2017): 151. [8] Panda, Ashok Kumar, Amit Kumar Dixit, Suvendu Rout, Baidyanath Mishra, Umesh Purad, and Sarbeswar Kar. "Ayurveda Practitioners Consensus to Develop Strategies for Prevention and Treatment of Corona Virus Disease (COVID-19)." Journal of Ayurveda and Integrated Medical Sciences (ISSN 2456-3110) 5, no. 1 (2020): 98-106. [9] Suchitra, M. R., and S. Parthasarathy. "Nutrition and corona virus: Plan a diet in a pandemic." International Journal of Research in Pharmaceutical Sciences 11, no. SPL1 (2020): 110-114. [10] Agarwal, Sangita, Srimoyee Saha, Tathagata Deb, and Soumendra Darbar. "Immunity augmenting food supplements for susceptible individuals in combating pandemic COVID19." [11] Sengupta, Sudip, and Saptarnee Dey. "Unearthing Asymptomatic COVID-19 Cases: How Nutrition and Dietary Management Can Render Immunity Against Pandemics?" [12] Jamison, Stephanie W. Function and Form in the-āya-Formations of the Rig Veda and Atharva Veda. No. 31. Vandenhoeck & Ruprecht, 1983.

